

Substituted [1,3,4]-oxadiazole, [1,3,4]-thiadiazole and [1,2,4]-triazole; synthesis, characterization and antimicrobial study

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Manuscript received 06 August 2009, revised 29 December 2010, accepted 20 June 2011

Abstract : Series of compounds 5-(benzotriazol-1-yl-methyl)-2-aryl/alkyl-amino-[1,3,4]-oxadiazoles, 5-(benzotriazol-1-yl-methyl)-2-aryl/alkyl-amino-[1,3,4]-thiadiazoles and 5-(benzotriazol-1-yl-methyl)-3-mercapto-4-aryl/alkyl-4H-[1,2,4]-triazoles have been synthesized by the oxidative cyclization of 2-benzotriazol-1-yl-N-aryl/alkyl thiocarbamido-acetamides using alkaline ethanolic solution of iodine containing potassium iodide, *ortho*-phosphoric acid and aqueous potassium hydroxide solution respectively. These compounds on acetylation afforded acetyl derivatives, on benzylation afforded benzoyl derivatives and on reaction with ethyl iodide afforded ethylmercapto derivatives. These compounds have been assayed for their antimicrobial activity against Gram-positive as well as Gram-negative microorganisms.

Keywords : Synthesis, antimicrobial activity, oxadiazole, thiadiazole, triazole.

Introduction

Synthesis of substituted [1,3,4]-oxadiazoles, [1,3,4]-thiadiazoles and [1,2,4]-triazoles and their biological¹ as well as antitumoral² activities have been reported earlier in few communications. The synthesis of [1,3,4]-oxadiazoles is of considerable interest due to their biological activities. Reported among these activities were nervous system depressing³, analgesic⁴, herbicidal⁵, muscle relaxant⁶ and tranquilizing⁷ activities. Also the synthesis of compounds incorporating [1,3,4]-thiadiazole and [1,2,4]-triazole rings has been attracting widespread attention due to their diverse pharmacological properties such as antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, analgesic and antitumoral activities⁸. The therapeutic effects of [1,2,4]-triazole containing compounds, have been well studied for a number of pathological conditions including inflammation, cancer, pain, tuberculosis or hypertension⁹. Although there are number of antibiotics which are commercially used in medicine, the synthesis of new compounds is of vital importance due to increasing drug resistance. Moreover it is important to obtain therapeutical compounds having less toxic effects. In view of the utility of these tri-heterocyclic compounds in various fields and as a part of wider programme to provide alternative routes for the synthesis of 5 and 6 membered heterocyclic compounds¹⁰, now the synthesis of tri-heterocyclic compounds viz. [1,3,4]-oxadiazoles, [1,3,4]-thiadiazoles and [1,2,4]-

triazoles by oxidative cyclization method is reported.

Results and discussion

Initially equimolar solution of benzotriazole (0.1 mol) in 1,4-dioxan and ethyl chloroacetate (0.1 mol) in the presence of anhydrous K₂CO₃ (4 g) were refluxed on a water bath for 6 h, to afford ethyl-benzotriazol-1-yl-acetate. Then the parent compound, benzotriazol-1-yl-acetic acid hydrazide (**1**) was prepared by refluxing the mixture of ethyl-benzotriazol-1-yl-acetate (0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mol) in 1,4-dioxan (15 ml) on a water bath for 5 h, cooled and the resulting solid was crystallised from chloroform-methanol (5 : 5 v/v) mixture¹¹.

It was transformed into 2-benzotriazol-1-yl-N-aryl/alkyl thiocarbamido-acetamides (**3a-h**) by condensing with N-aryl/alkyl isothiocyanates (**2a-h**) (0.01 mol) in refluxing carbontetrachloride medium for 2.5 h. Compounds **3a-h** were then transformed into 5-(benzotriazol-1-yl-methyl)-2-aryl/alkyl-amino-[1,3,4]-oxadiazoles (**4a-h**) by oxidative cyclization using alkaline ethanolic solution of iodine containing potassium iodide with evolution of hydrogen sulphide gas. Compounds **4a-h** on acylation with acetic anhydride and glacial acetic acid afforded acetyl derivatives (**5a-h**).

Compounds **3a-h** were then reacted with *ortho*-phosphoric acid by dropwise addition of *ortho*-phosphoric acid

with constant stirring for 30 min and allowing to stand at room temperature for 3 h to yield 5-(benzotriazol-1-yl-methyl)-2-aryl/alkyl-amino-[1,3,4]-thiadiazoles (**6a-h**) by oxidative cyclization. Compounds **6a-h** were benzoylated using benzoyl chloride and 10% sodium hydroxide solution to yield benzoyl derivatives (**7a-h**).

Compounds **3a-h** were also reacted with potassium hydroxide by dropwise addition of 5% aqueous potassium hydroxide solution with constant stirring for 30 min and allowing to stand at room temperature for 3 h to yield 5-(benzotriazol-1-yl-methyl)-3-mercapto-4-aryl/alkyl-4H-[1,2,4]-triazoles (**8a-h**) by oxidative cyclization. Compounds **8a-h** were reacted with ethyl iodide followed by the basification with dilute ammonium hydroxide to afford ethylmercapto derivatives (**9a-h**) (Scheme 1).

Antimicrobial activity :

The synthesized compounds **4a-h**, **6a-h** and **8a-h** were screened for their antibacterial activity using cup plate diffusion method¹². The bacterial organisms used included both Gram-positive as well as Gram-negative strains like *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *S. typhi*, *B. subtilis* and *A. aerogenes*. Sensitivity plates were seeded with a bacterial inoculum of 1×10^6 CIU ml⁻¹ and each well (diameter 10 mm) was loaded with 0.1 ml of test compound solution (1000 µg ml⁻¹) in DMF, so that concentration of each test compound was 100 µg ml⁻¹. The zones of inhibition were recorded after incubation for 24 h at 37 °C, using Vernier caliper. Inhibition zone record of the compounds clearly indicated that **4c**, **6d**, **6e**, **8c** and **8g** were highly

Scheme 1

Deohate : Substituted [1,3,4]-oxadiazole, [1,3,4]-thiadiazole and [1,2,4]-triazole; synthesis *etc.*

active against *S. typhi*, *E. coli* and moderately active against *S. aureus* and *A. aerogenes*. Majority of the compounds were found inactive against *B. subtilis* (Table 1).

Experimental

The melting points of all synthesized compounds were recorded using hot paraffin-bath and are uncorrected.

Table 1. Antibacterial and antifungal activity of compounds 4a-h, 6a-h and 8a-h

Comps.	Antibacterial activity					Antifungal activity
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. typhi</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>A. aerogenes</i>	<i>A. niger</i> (Concn. 1%)
4a	+	-	+	-	+	-
4b	+	-	+	+	+	+
4c	+++	++	+++	+	++	++
4d	+	+	+	-	-	+++
4e	++	+	-	+	-	++
4f	-	++	-	-	-	+
4g	-	+	-	+	+	+++
4h	++	-	+	-	+	-
6a	-	-	+	-	++	+
6b	+	+	+	++	+	+
6c	+	+	++	+	+	+++
6d	+++	++	+++	+	++	+
6e	+++	++	+++	++	++	-
6f	-	+	-	-	+	-
6g	+	-	+	+	+	++
6h	++	-	++	+	++	+
8a	+	+	+	-	-	+
8b	-	++	+	-	-	++
8c	+++	++	+++	+	++	+
8d	-	-	-	+	-	-
8e	++	+	++	-	+	+++
8f	+	+	+	+	+	+
8g	+++	++	+++	+	++	+++
8h	-	+	+	-	+	+

(-) : Inactive (12 mm and less), (+) : Weakly active (13-16 mm), (++) : Moderately active (17-20 mm), (+++) : Highly active (21 mm and above).

To determine minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC), the serial dilution technique¹³ was followed using nutrient broth medium. The MIC values of compounds 4c, 6d and 8c, were determined against *S. aureus*, *S. typhi* and *E. coli*, which were found to be 70, 82 and 74 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ respectively.

Screening of these compounds 4a-h, 6a-h and 8a-h having the concentration 1%, for antifungal activity using paper disc method¹⁴ showed that 4d, 4g, 6c, 8e and 8g were highly active against *A. niger*, whereas other compounds showed low to moderate activity. The zones of inhibition were recorded after incubation for 48 h at 37 °C (Table 1).

Chemicals used were of AR grade. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded with TMS as internal standard using CDCl₃ and DMSO-*d*₆ as solvents. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer in the range 4000-400 cm⁻¹ in nuol mull and as KBr pellete. Purity of the compounds was checked on silica gel-G plates by TLC.

Initially equimolar solution of benzotriazole (0.1 mol) in 1,4-dioxan and ethyl chloroacetate (0.1 mol) in the presence of anhydrous K₂CO₃ (4 g) was refluxed on a water bath for 6 h, cooled and the solid obtained was crystallised from methanol to afford ethyl-benzotriazol-1-yl-acetate. Then the parent compound, benzotriazol-1-yl-acetic acid hydrazide (1) was prepared by refluxing

the mixture of ethyl-benzotriazol-1-yl-acetate (0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mol) in 1,4-dioxan (15 ml) on a water bath for 5 h, cooled and the resulting solid was crystallised from chloroform-methanol (5 : 5 v/v) mixture, by reported method.

Synthesis of 2-benzotriazol-1-yl-N-phenyl thiocarbamido-acetamide (3a) :

The compound 2-benzotriazol-1-yl-N-phenyl thiocarbamide-acetamide (**3a**) was prepared by refluxing the mixture of benzotriazol-1-yl-acetic acid hydrazide (**1**) (0.01 mol) and N-phenyl isothiocyanate (**2a**) (0.01 mol) in carbontetrachloride (15 ml) for 2.5 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and the solid residue obtained was crystallised from ethanol, **3a** (75%). m.p. 177 °C (Found : C, 54.98; H, 4.26; N, 25.40; S, 9.44. Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₄N₆OS : C, 55.20; H, 4.32; N, 25.75; S, 9.82%); ν_{\max} 3423, 3370, 3257 (NH), 1690 (C=O), 1596 (N=N), 1306 (C-N), 1247 (C=S), 1217 cm⁻¹ (N-N)¹⁵; δ (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆) 8.05 (1H, s, CO-NH-N), 7.56 (2H, s, benzotriazole), 7.55 (2H, s, benzotriazole), 7.21–7.37 (5H, m, Ar-H), 3.89 (2H, s, N-CH₂-CO), 3.81 (1H, s, CS-NH-Ar), 2.13 (1H, s, CS-NH-N); MS : *m/z* 325 (M⁺-H), 249 (M⁺-Ph), 208 (M⁺-benzotriazole), 166 (M⁺-benzotriazole-CH₂-CO), 190 (M⁺-PhNHCS), 118 (benzotriazole⁺), 77 (Ph⁺). This reaction was extended to synthesize other compounds **3b-h** using different N-aryl/alkyl isothiocyanates (**2b-h**) : **3b** (70%), m.p. 198 °C; **c** (72%), m.p. 169 °C; **d** (71%), m.p. 174 °C; **e** (80%), m.p. 213 °C; **f** (70%), m.p. 186 °C; **g** (81%), m.p. 170 °C; **h** (74%), m.p. 231 °C.

Synthesis of 5-(benzotriazol-1-yl-methyl)-2-phenylamino-[1,3,4]-oxadiazole (4a) :

A paste of 2-benzotriazol-1-yl-N-phenyl thiocarbamido-acetamide (**3a**) (0.01 mol) was prepared in ethanol. To it iodine solution in ethanolic potassium hydroxide containing potassium iodide was added dropwise with constant stirring. The colour of iodine was initially disappeared. The addition was continued till violet colour of the iodine persisted. The reaction mixture was left overnight at room temperature, granular solid was separated. It was washed with distilled water, crystallised from ethanol and identified as 5-(benzotriazol-1-yl-methyl)-2-phenylamino-[1,3,4]-oxadiazole (**4a**) (70%), m.p. 214 °C (Found : C, 60.98; H, 4.02; N, 28.18. Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₂N₆O : C, 61.64; H,

4.14; N, 28.75%); ν_{\max} 3297 (NH), 1684 (N=N), 1595 (C=N), 1370 (C-O), 1287 (C-N), 1243 cm⁻¹ (N-N); δ (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆) 7.96 (2H, s, benzotriazole), 7.47 (2H, s, benzotriazole), 6.42–7.08 (5H, m, Ar-H), 4.90 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 4.2 (1H, s, NH); MS : *m/z* 291 (M⁺-H), 215 (M⁺-Ph), 200 (M⁺-PhNH), 174 (M⁺-benzotriazole), 160 (M⁺-benzotriazole-CH₂), 118 (benzotriazole⁺), 92 (PhNH⁺). This reaction was extended to synthesize other compounds **4b-h** : **4b** (77%), m.p. 183 °C (Found : C, 62.28; H, 4.42; N, 26.88. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₄N₆O : C, 62.74; H, 4.61; N, 27.43%); ν_{\max} 3416 (NH), 1632 (N=N), 1568 (C=N), 1306 (C-O), 1269 (C-N), 1238 cm⁻¹ (N-N); δ (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆) 7.96 (2H, s, benzotriazole), 7.47 (2H, s, benzotriazole), 6.30–6.94 (4H, m, Ar-H), 4.91 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 4.1 (1H, s, NH), 2.34 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃); **c** (75%), m.p. 176 °C (Found : C, 62.65; H, 4.55; N, 27.05. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₄N₆O : C, 62.74; H, 4.61; N, 27.43%); **d** (70%), m.p. 195 °C (Found : C, 62.59; H, 4.33; N, 27.11. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₄N₆O : C, 62.74; H, 4.61; N, 27.43%); **e** (77%), m.p. 202 °C (Found : C, 54.96; H, 3.18; N, 25.61. Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₁N₆OCl : C, 55.14; H, 3.39; N, 25.72%); **f** (72%), m.p. 188 °C (Found: C, 54.76; H, 3.23; N, 25.58. Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₁N₆OCl : C, 55.14; H, 3.39; N, 25.72%); **g** (75%), m.p. 194 °C (Found : C, 54.83; H, 3.33; N, 25.69. Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₁N₆OCl : C, 55.14; H, 3.39; N, 25.72%); **h** (65%), m.p. 176 °C (Found : C, 57.11; H, 5.71; N, 30.60. Calcd. for C₁₃H₁₆N₆O : C, 57.34; H, 5.92; N, 30.86%).

Synthesis of 5-(benzotriazol-1-yl-methyl)-2-phenylacetamido-[1,3,4]-oxadiazole (5a) :

A mixture of 5-(benzotriazol-1-yl-methyl)-2-phenylamino-[1,3,4]-oxadiazole (**4a**) (0.01 mol) and acetic anhydride (0.01 mol) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was refluxed for 2.5 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured in a little crushed ice with water, a cream coloured solid precipitated was crystallised from aqueous ethanol to give **5a** (80%), m.p. 172 °C (Found : C, 60.83; H, 4.09; N, 25.05. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₄N₆O₂ : C, 61.07; H, 4.22; N, 25.14%); ν_{\max} 1691 (C=O), 1636 (N=N), 1607 (C=N), 1371 (C-O), 1342 (C-N), 1247 cm⁻¹ (N-N); δ (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆) 7.96 (2H, s, benzotriazole), 7.47 (2H, s, benzotriazole), 6.98–7.67 (5H, m, Ar-H), 4.90 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 2.02 (3H, s, CO-CH₃); MS : *m/z* 319 (M⁺-CH₃), 291 (M⁺-COCH₃), 257 (M⁺-Ph), 216 (M⁺-

benzotriazole), 202 (M^+ -benzotriazole- CH_2), 200 (M^+ -PhNCOCH₃), 134 (PhNCOCH₃⁺), 77 (Ph⁺). This reaction was extended to synthesize other acetyl derivatives, **5b-h** from **4b-h** respectively : **5b** (70%), m.p. 174 °C; **c** (65%), m.p. 164 °C; **d** (70%), m.p. 213 °C; **e** (70%), m.p. 202 °C; **f** (76%), m.p. 184 °C; **g** (75%), m.p. 195 °C; **h** (71%), m.p. 176 °C.

Synthesis of 5-(benzotriazol-1-yl-methyl)-2-phenylamino-[1,3,4]-thiadiazole (6a) :

To the 2-benzotriazol-1-yl-*N*-phenyl thiocarbamido-acetamide (**3a**) (0.01 mol) *ortho*-phosphoric acid (10 ml) was added dropwise with constant stirring. Stirring was continued for 30 min. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool and left at room temperature for 3 h. On cooling the reaction mixture and pouring it in water, an off white coloured solid was precipitated. It was washed with distilled water, crystallised from aqueous ethanol and identified as 5-(benzotriazol-1-yl-methyl)-2-phenylamino-[1,3,4]-thiadiazole (**6a**) (72%), m.p. 197 °C (Found : C, 58.12; H, 3.70; N, 26.99; S, 10.31. Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₂N₆S : C, 58.43; H, 3.92; N, 27.25; S, 10.40%); ν_{max} 3392 (NH), 1629 (N=N), 1554 (C=N), 1353 (C-N), 1254 (N-N), 705 cm⁻¹ (C-S); δ (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆) 7.98 (2H, s, benzotriazole), 7.46 (2H, s, benzotriazole), 6.42–7.10 (5H, m, Ar-H), 4.96 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 4.0 (1H, s, NH); MS : *m/z* 308 (M⁺), 307 (M⁺-H), 231 (M⁺-Ph), 216 (M⁺-PhNH), 190 (M⁺-benzotriazole), 176 (M⁺-benzotriazole-CH₂), 118 (benzotriazole⁺), 92 (PhNH⁺), 77 (Ph⁺). This reaction was extended to synthesize other compounds **6b-h** : **6b** (78%), m.p. 196 °C (Found : C, 59.11; H, 4.19; N, 25.83; S, 9.45. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₄N₆S : C, 59.61; H, 4.38; N, 26.07; S, 9.95%); ν_{max} 3423 (NH), 1637 (N=N), 1596 (C=N), 1307 (C-N), 1218 (N-N), 690 cm⁻¹ (C-S); δ (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆) 7.98 (2H, s, benzotriazole), 7.46 (2H, s, benzotriazole), 6.28–6.98 (4H, m, Ar-H), 4.97 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 3.9 (1H, s, NH), 2.35 (3H, s, Ar-CH₂); **c** (68%), m.p. 179 °C (Found : C, 59.43; H, 4.27; N, 25.94; S, 9.66. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₄N₆S : C, 59.61; H, 4.38; N, 26.07; S, 9.95%); **d** (75%), m.p. 213 °C (Found : C, 59.37; H, 4.32; N, 26.00; S, 9.78. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₄N₆S : C, 59.61; H, 4.38; N, 26.07; S, 9.95%); **e** (70%), m.p. 164 °C (Found : C, 52.12; H, 3.19; N, 24.49; S, 9.26. Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₁N₆SCl : C, 52.56; H, 3.23; N, 24.51; S, 9.35%); **f** (82%), m.p. 238

°C (Found : C, 52.36; H, 3.13; N, 24.31; S, 9.14. Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₁N₆SCl : C, 52.56; H, 3.23; N, 24.51; S, 9.35%); **g** (70%), m.p. 174 °C (Found : C, 52.29; H, 3.21; N, 24.42; S, 9.23. Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₁N₆SCl : C, 52.56; H, 3.23; N, 24.51; S, 9.35%); **h** (74%), m.p. 189 °C (Found : C, 53.91; H, 5.53; N, 28.97; S, 11.01. Calcd. for C₁₃H₁₆N₆S : C, 54.15; H, 5.59; N, 29.14; S, 11.12%).

Synthesis of 5-(benzotriazol-1-yl-methyl)-2-phenylbenzamido-[1,3,4]-thiadiazole (7a) :

To the suspension of 5-(benzotriazol-1-yl-methyl)-2-phenylamino-[1,3,4]-thiadiazole (**6a**) (0.01 mol) in 10% sodium hydroxide solution (10 ml), benzoyl chloride (0.01 mol) was added within half an hour with vigorous shaking and maintaining the temperature below 5 °C. The reaction mixture was poured in a little crushed ice with water, a whitish yellow solid isolated was crystallised from aqueous ethanol to give **7a** (75%), m.p. 205 °C (Found : C, 63.82; H, 3.88; N, 20.27; S, 7.62. Calcd. for C₂₂H₁₆N₆OS : C, 64.06; H, 3.91; N, 20.37; S, 7.77%); ν_{max} 1682 (C=O), 1621 (N=N), 1599 (C=N), 1300 (C-N), 1269 (N-N), 701 cm⁻¹ (C-S); δ (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆) 7.98 (2H, s, benzotriazole), 7.46 (2H, s, benzotriazole), 6.97–7.95 (10H, m, Ar-H), 4.96 (2H, s, N-CH₂); MS : *m/z* 335 (M⁺-Ph), 307 (M⁺-PhCO), 217 (M⁺-benzotriazole), 216 (M⁺-PhNCOPh), 203 (M⁺-benzotriazole-CH₂), 77 (Ph⁺). This reaction was extended to synthesize other acetyl derivatives, **7b-h** from **6a-h** respectively : **7b** (70%), m.p. 192 °C; **c** (75%), m.p. 207 °C; **d** (78%), m.p. 185 °C; **e** (72%), m.p. 244 °C; **f** (81%), m.p. 219 °C; **g** (70%), m.p. 229 °C; **h** (67%), m.p. 168 °C.

Synthesis of 5-(benzotriazol-1-yl-methyl)-3-mercapto-4-phenyl-4H-[1,2,4]-triazole (8a) :

To the 2-benzotriazol-1-yl-*N*-phenyl thiocarbamido-acetamide (**3a**) (0.01 mol) 5% aqueous potassium hydroxide solution (10 ml) was added dropwise with constant stirring. Stirring was continued for 30 min. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool and left at room temperature for 3 h. On cooling the reaction mixture and pouring it in water, a dirty white coloured solid was precipitated. It was washed with distilled water, crystallised from warm water with ethanol and identified as 5-(benzotriazol-1-yl-

methyl)-3-mercapto-4-phenyl-4*H*-[1,2,4]-triazole (**8a**) (75%), m.p. 227 °C (Found : C, 58.28; H, 3.79; N, 27.14; S, 10.23. Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₂N₆S : C, 58.43; H, 3.92; N, 27.25; S, 10.40%); ν_{\max} 3320 (SH), 1644 (N=N), 1599 (C=N), 1333 (C-N), 1239 (N-N), 738 cm⁻¹ (C-S); δ (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆) 7.97 (2H, s, benzotriazole), 7.45 (2H, s, benzotriazole), 6.40–7.24 (5H, m, Ar-H), 4.95 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 3.22 (1H, s, SH); MS : *m/z* 307 (M⁺-H), 275 (M⁺-SH), 231 (M⁺-Ph), 190 (M⁺-benzotriazole), 176 (M⁺-benzotriazole-CH₂), 118 (benzotriazole⁺), 77 (Ph⁺), 33 (SH⁺). This reaction was extended to synthesize other compounds **8b-h** : **8b** (70%), m.p. 187 °C (Found : C, 59.27; H, 4.13; N, 25.85; S, 9.67. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₄N₆S : C, 59.61; H, 4.38; N, 26.07; S, 9.95%); ν_{\max} 3328 (SH), 1591 (N=N), 1510 (C=N), 1312 (C-N), 1237 (N-N), 697 cm⁻¹ (C-S); δ (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆) 7.97 (2H, s, benzotriazole), 7.45 (2H, s, benzotriazole), 6.38–7.21 (4H, m, Ar-H), 4.96 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 3.21 (1H, s, SH), 2.35 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃); **c** (75%), m.p. 201 °C (Found : C, 59.40; H, 4.29; N, 25.77; S, 9.89. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₄N₆S : C, 59.61; H, 4.38; N, 26.07; S, 9.95%); **d** (72%), m.p. 186 °C (Found : C, 59.12; H, 4.24; N, 25.73; S, 9.81. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₄N₆S : C, 59.61; H, 4.38; N, 26.07; S, 9.95%); **e** (70%), m.p. 238 °C (Found : C, 52.41; H, 3.20; N, 24.50; S, 9.24. Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₁N₆SCl : C, 52.56; H, 3.23; N, 24.51; S, 9.35%); **f** (73%), m.p. 222 °C (Found : C, 52.35; H, 3.17; N, 24.18; S, 9.20. Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₁N₆SCl : C, 52.56; H, 3.23; N, 24.51; S, 9.35%); **g** (71%), m.p. 186 °C (Found : C, 52.11; H, 3.16; N, 24.30; S, 9.18. Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₁N₆SCl : C, 52.56; H, 3.23; N, 24.51; S, 9.35%); **h** (80%), m.p. 185 °C (Found : C, 53.79; H, 5.55; N, 28.93; S, 11.07. Calcd. for C₁₃H₁₆N₆S : C, 54.15; H, 5.59; N, 29.14; S, 11.12%).

Synthesis of 5-(benzotriazol-1-yl-methyl)-3-ethylmercapto-4-phenyl-4H-[1,2,4]-triazole (9a) :

A mixture of 5-(benzotriazol-1-yl-methyl)-3-mercapto-4-phenyl-4*H*-[1,2,4]-triazole (**8a**) (0.01 mol) and ethyl iodide (0.01 mol) in ethanol (10 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured in a little crushed ice with water, white solid precipitated was identified as hydroiodide of 5-(benzotriazol-1-yl-methyl)-3-ethylmercapto-4-phenyl-4*H*-[1,2,4]-triazole. It was basified with dilute ammonium hydroxide and crystallised from ethanol to give a free base (**9a**) (74%), m.p. 205 °C

(Found : C, 59.81; H, 4.65; N, 24.57; S, 9.48. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₆N₆S : C, 60.69; H, 4.79; N, 24.98; S, 9.53%); ν_{\max} 1681 (N=N), 1591 (C=N), 1280 (C-N), 1276 (N-N), 688 cm⁻¹ (C-S); δ (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆) 7.97 (2H, s, benzotriazole), 7.45 (2H, s, benzotriazole), 6.42–7.60 (5H, m, Ar-H), 4.95 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 2.96 (2H, q, S-CH₂), 1.20 (3H, t, -CH₃); MS : *m/z* 336 (M⁺), 321 (M⁺-CH₃), 307 (M⁺-C₂H₅), 275 (M⁺-C₂H₅S), 259 (M⁺-Ph), 218 (M⁺-benzotriazole), 204 (M⁺-benzotriazole-CH₂), 118 (benzotriazole⁺). This reaction was extended to synthesize other ethylmercapto derivatives (**9b-h**) : **9b** (70%), m.p. 177 °C; **c** (72%), m.p. 159 °C; **d** (75%), m.p. 197 °C; **e** (77%), m.p. 224 °C; **f** (75%), m.p. 209 °C; **g** (70%), m.p. 228 °C; **h** (68%), m.p. 177 °C.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Director, RSIC, Central Drug Research Institute, Chandigarh and Director, ICT, Hyderabad for providing analytical and spectral data. Authors are also thankful to Dr. V. D. Nanoty, Principal, Shri Radhakisan Laxminarayan Toshniwal College of Science, Akola for providing necessary facilities.

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Deohate : Substituted [1,3,4]-oxadiazole, [1,3,4]-thiadiazole and [1,2,4]-triazole; synthesis *etc.*

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